

Does early childhood education reduce inequalities in educational outcomes for children facing multiple disadvantages:

A systematic review on longitudinal and quasi-experimental studies

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A systematic review on longitudinal and quasi-experimental studies
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Introduction

Since the 2000's, there has been a rapid emergence of early childhood education (ECE) policies globally (Shawar & Shiffman, 2017). This growth in attention is due to an increase in evidence that targeting interventions at the early childhood stage can lead to more positive life outcomes for children, especially those facing intersectional barriers to education (Melhuish, 2011). Despite the wide implementation of ECE policies and greater research attention devoted to the field, there remain unanswered questions regarding the most effective ECE interventions which mitigate educational inequalities.

This systematic review will provide a cross-national evaluation of early childhood policies, focusing on reducing educational inequalities amongst the most disadvantaged children. This report represents a deliverable of the Strategies for Achieving Equity and Inclusion in Education, Training and Learning in Democratic Europe (STRIDE) Project. Through its deliverables and outputs, the STRIDE Project seeks to provide a new, comprehensive and comparative knowledge-base on effective education reforms, policy initiatives and interventions which aim to reduce educational inequalities. As such, this report and its findings will provide some evidence which can aid researchers, educators and policymakers in crafting and implementing interventions which attempt to mitigate educational inequalities across the globe in the short, medium and long term.

Through this systematic review, we aim to identify effective ECE practices and interventions, targeting migrants, minorities and individuals with low socio-economic status. We foreground this report using a sociological background to understand these groups. In many cases, migrant and minority groups are understood and defined by the state using statistical and political categories, which homogenises ethnicity, race and lived experience (Elrick & Farah Schwartzman, 2015). We avoid homogenous understandings of these groups by using less rigid statistical definitions and underscoring societal constructions and categorisations of minorities.

We define migrant and minority groups using definitions by Gwendolyn Sasse and Eiko Thielemann. National minorities refer to non-dominant groups in society, socially, politically and culturally, who share cultural characteristics distinct from dominant populations (Sasse & Thielemann, 2005). Many individuals who are considered minorities also have migrant backgrounds, which often obfuscates understandings and national categorisations of these groups (Sasse & Thielemann, 2005). Nonetheless, migrants are understood, in this report, as individuals who have resided outside of their birth country for a specific time period, often 12 months or longer (Sasse & Thielemann, 2005). The Office for National Statistics defines socio-economic status as a measure of employment, occupational conditions and income (“The National Statistics Socio-economic classification,” n.d.). In this study, we are cognizant that these determinants are not conclusive of social barriers and life chances.

Regarding early childhood interventions, many cover a number of sectors like health, economics, education and development (Nelson et al., 2003). While interventions across these sectors have generated meaningful benefits for children facing intersectional disadvantages, this study focuses primarily on educational interventions, with some consideration of cross-sectoral influences. Specifically, we examine early childhood initiatives aimed at directly improving educational outcomes and exclude interventions which solely target teacher and staff development. This strategic focus enables a critical examination of the educational interventions that directly address educational inequalities within our target population.

In this systematic review, we examine educational interventions on a global scale. This contributes to the literature on Early Childhood Education, as many studies have focused on particular interventions and facets of ECE related to sustainability (Ardoin & Bowers, 2020; Güler Yıldız et al., 2020), health outcomes (Jellyman & Spencer, 2008; Pillas et al., 2014) and educators (Bubikova-Moan et al., 2019 & Linder & Simpson, 2017). Our scale and research focus provide a more comprehensive examination of the effectiveness of early childhood education interventions across time, space and location.

Given that the early development of cognitive and behavioural skills is often linked to more positive academic trajectories and life outcomes, this study is organised around educational interventions that measure academic achievement, behavioural skill development and retention (McCoy et al., 2017). In the evaluations throughout this report, academic achievement is typically assessed through standardised test scores, cognitive tests as well as teacher and parental reports. Behavioural skills are evaluated through observational assessments, teacher and parental feedback and specialised screening tools. Retention is measured through indicators such as chronic absenteeism, matriculation into higher education, dropout rates, incarceration and crime statistics and other adult life outcomes. Collectively, these measures provide a robust framework for identifying and assessing intervention outcomes which address educational inequalities and cycles of poverty for groups facing intersectional disadvantages.

In this report, we have also prioritised studies that employ longitudinal and quasi-experimental research designs. Longitudinal studies are particularly critical in ECE research, as they allow stakeholders to understand how ECE policies influence later development and educational outcomes (Centre for Early Childhood, 2002). In addition, randomised controlled trials and quasi-experimental methods have continuously proven effective in evaluating policy impacts (Hariton & Locascio, 2018). Randomised control trials significantly reduce bias by balancing participant characteristics, allowing researchers to examine cause and effect relationships (Hariton & Locascio, 2018). Accordingly, we have limited our study outputs to those employing these methodologies to provide the most reliable and impactful insights.

Research Question

With the aims of this systematic review and our targeted framework in mind, we have developed the following research question:

To what extent are early childhood education policies/ interventions effective at promoting academic achievement, improving behavioural functioning and increasing retention, discerning by social categories that include migrant, minority and/or low SES status.

Methods

This report primarily focuses on a qualitative literature review, utilizing content analysis to gain insights into the topic by synthesizing and identifying emerging themes. Following the approach of Hanelt et al., (2021) and Ratajczak (2022), the review process consists of three main steps: (i) identification of relevant databases and data collection; (ii) data analysis; and (iii) synthesis.

Database

This systematic review was initially undertaken by completing searches for protocols in Google Scholar before the articles were screened manually. Google Scholar was chosen as our main database because it often provides a broader and more comprehensive coverage of academic literature compared to traditional databases like Scopus and Web of Science. In addition, Google Scholar's coverage is wider than other academic databases which is convenient for identifying articles corresponding to exact and related search terms rather than direct matches (Donbavand & Hoskins, 2021; Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020).

Search strategies

A search strategy based on a PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) was adopted in the current study which consists of three main stages: identification, screening and included.

Identification

In the first stage, the search was undertaken using Google Scholar. Based on a thorough analysis of the literature and the research team's discussions, we created keyword lists and synonyms for the search protocols. The list of keywords is as follows (see Table 1).

Table 1: Lists of keywords

Dependent variable	Factors (OR within)	Google Scholar
Educational achievement	Early childhood intervention, early years' intervention, early childhood reform, early childhood project, preschool program, foundation phase*, educational outcomes, educational attainment, educational achievement, impacts, effectiveness*, longitudinal research, panel study	Title, abstract, keywords

During this stage, we used Google Scholar's sorting tool to filter and narrow the scope of articles. To that end, the study's time period is limited to 2000-2025. The main reason for this, as stated by Higgins & Green (2011), is that the article publication date should be limited to ensure the most up-to-date, pertinent research. This does not mean that the policy duration lies between this period, as some of the articles included in the report examine policies before 2000. Secondly, our inclusion criteria are limited to only empirical articles. The third and final inclusion criterion is

English-language articles, as the team did not have sufficient resources for translation. A total of 9280 articles were found in the initial search. By default, Google Scholar allows downloading and working on the first 1000 relevant articles only. The 1000 article output is discerned by search terms which produce the most cited articles.

Screening

In the screening stage, title screening was completed manually in which 736 articles were excluded based on relevance. An additional 155 articles were excluded due to duplication. A total of 96 articles were chosen for the full-text screening stage. To be eligible for inclusion, a study must focus on early childhood education policies, initiatives or interventions that aim to reduce inequalities in educational achievement and satisfy the following additional criteria:

- (i) The program or intervention must have begun during a child's preschool years (before kindergarten based on specific context).
- (ii) The program or intervention must focus on educational development or mixed purposes that contain educational elements.
- (iii) Research must be reported in journal articles, book chapters and unpublished reports between 2000-2025
- (iv) Outcome measures must include indicators of educational achievement (test scores, grades), children's behavioural development or retention.
- (v) Methodologies must include randomised control trials or quasi-experimental approaches.
- (vi) Studies must focus explicitly on migrants, minority groups or individuals with low SES status.

Included

Following the rigorous procedure of screening articles, **37 full-text articles** were selected for data analysis. Of these, 21 examined educational achievement, 9 addressed behavioural advancement outcomes and 7 focused on student retention.

During the full-text screening process, articles were organised according to measured policy outcomes by three themes: (1) academic achievement, (2) behavioural advancement and (3) retention. These themes enable us to gauge effectiveness measures for early childhood interventions pertaining to our target populations. Academic achievement, determined primarily through test scores, cognitive assessments and teacher and parental evaluations, is the measure used most frequently throughout the literature. Consequently, articles that are centred on behaviour and retention often include standard measures for academic achievement to supplement their findings. The malleability of the themes can provide additional evidence of policy effectiveness, as one measure often corroborates the success or failure of another in many of the evaluations.

Within the major themes, academic achievement, behavioural advancement, and retention, the articles were grouped according to subcategories which reference the type of early childhood policy evaluation. We begin each section exploring targeted and general expansions of early childhood education policies and follow with long-term evaluations.

Many of the articles reference the same or similar early childhood education policies. However, these articles are not duplicates, focusing, instead, on differing outcomes and timeframes. Including articles which reference the same policy is useful to evaluate the credibility and validity of earlier evaluations over time. These articles are also helpful as they report data on how interventions affect some outcomes and subgroups differently.

Results

Achievement

In this section, we focus on articles which evaluate the effectiveness of early childhood education interventions through achievement measures. Although achievement measures, like assessments and test scores, have become more contentious approaches of determining educational success in recent years, these measures continue to be used most often in education policy evaluations (Schneider, 2017). Being cognizant of the arguments for and against using measures like test scores to determine educational success, we outline the current scholarship in the field with a critical eye toward more effective and ethical practices for children and youth.

Table two presents an overview of the articles in this section.

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Table 2: Academic Achievement Outcomes of Early Childhood Interventions

Subtheme	Author(s) (Year)	Country/ Context	Intervention Type	Study Design	Key Achievement Findings
Targeted Programs	Fantuzzo et al. (2011)	USA	EPIC curriculum (Head Start)	RCT	Significant gains in mathematics and listening comprehension; modest literacy effects
	Buyse et al. (2010)	USA	Nuestros Niños (dual-language learners)	Quasi-experimental	Improvements in classroom literacy quality; limited direct child achievement gains
	Drange & Telle (2015)	Norway	Free preschool for migrant children	Quasi-experimental	Higher school-entry test scores; sustained reading and math gains
	de Haan et al. (2013)	Netherlands	Targeted vs mixed classrooms	Quasi-experimental	Mixed classrooms outperformed targeted-only disadvantaged classrooms
Community-Based / Localised	Bagnato et al. (2002)	USA	Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative	Longitudinal	Above-average literacy and math skills; low special education placement
	Melhuish et al. (2008)	England	Sure Start (early phase)	Quasi-experimental	Mixed early effects; later improvements after programme refinement
	Sammons et al. (2015)	England	Sure Start Children's Centres	Longitudinal Quasi-experimental	Evidence of positive outcomes in improving child behavioural and social skills, with more modest gains in cognitive development
	Evangelou et al. (2007)	England	PEEP Programme	Longitudinal	Gains in vocabulary, phonological awareness, early numeracy
	Katz et al. (2010)	Australia	Communities for Children Initiative	Longitudinal Quasi-Experimental	Improvements in vocabulary, phonological awareness, early numeracy skills and other early learning milestones

	Goodson et al. 2000	USA	Comprehensive Child Development Programme	Longitudinal Quasi-Experimental	No statistically significant outcomes
Universal ECE Expansions	Chen et al. (2019)	China	One Village One Preschool	Longitudinal	Higher elementary achievement; closing rural achievement gaps
	Aboud (2006)	Bangladesh	Rural preschool expansion	Quasi-experimental	Improved vocabulary, reasoning, and school readiness
	Ghirardi et al. (2023)	Germany	ECEC expansion	Longitudinal	Stronger math and vocabulary effects for low-SES children
	Klein & Becker 2017	Germany	Preschool Attendance	Longitudinal Quasi-Experimental	For children from Turkish backgrounds, preschool attendance for 36 months, 26 hours per week, improves German vocabulary
	Leuven et al. (2010)	Netherlands	Earlier school entry	Quasi-experimental	Reduced achievement gaps for disadvantaged and minority students
Long-Term Evaluations	Yao & Hearn (2003)	USA	SC Early Childhood Programme	Longitudinal	Higher test scores through third grade
	Dong (2009)	USA	Head Start	Longitudinal Quasi-Experimental	No statistically significant difference between Head Start participants and those in other centre-based programmes on reading and math achievement
	Kim (2013)	USA	Head Start	Longitudinal	Sustained math gains for African American students
	Therese Pigott et al. (2005)	USA	Head Start	Longitudinal	Compared to children of similar socio-economic status, Head Start participants scored higher than their peers. When compared to affluent children, achievement gaps remained

Initial Evaluations

Targeted Programs

There is evidence that preschool participation can lead to positive effects, including numerous educational benefits for children who attend early childhood programmes compared to those who do not (Barnett, 2008). As the evidence base supporting early childhood education has grown, stakeholders, policymakers and researchers have increasingly shifted their focus from evaluating preschool programmes in general to examining the implementation of enriched, targeted curricula (Nguyen et al. 2019).

To begin this systematic review, we will first examine programmes with targeted curricula and local interventions to address specific needs. We will then move toward an evaluation of more generalised early childhood initiatives.

In recent years, researchers have found that the implementation of targeted curricula into preschool programmes often results in greater and more sustained benefits for children (Rege et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2018). Notable examples include the United States' integrated Head Start curriculum, the EPIC programme, and the Nuestros Niños Professional Development Programme, each designed to narrow the educational gap between disadvantaged groups and their peers.

The EPIC curriculum, implemented in the United States' Head Start programmes, specifically targeted children from low socioeconomic backgrounds and aimed to mitigate educational disparities between disadvantaged children and their peers. EPIC was implemented in response to a preschool curriculum evaluation which found that no single comprehensive curriculum produced significant effects in math, language or literacy outcomes when compared to control groups (Fantuzzo et al., 2011). With these outcomes in mind, the EPIC curriculum was developed using evidence-based modules focused on cultivating critical cognitive and language skills, which were piloted through randomised controlled trials to evaluate their effective-

ness prior to broader implementation (Fantuzzo et al., 2011). EPIC emphasised "alphabet knowledge and phonemic awareness, print concept, vocabulary, listening comprehension and mathematics" (Fantuzzo et al., 2011, p. 769), and included both small group activities and home-based learning to reinforce these areas.

When compared to other curricula, researchers found that EPIC led to greater student achievement and faster growth rates in mathematics and listening comprehension (Fantuzzo et al., 2011). While participation in EPIC also showed increased growth rates in literacy, these gains were not statistically significant relative to comparison curricula (Fantuzzo et al., 2011). Although children's literacy gains from EPIC are unclear, the curriculum was successful at producing significant improvements in more than one educational domain, which had proven increasingly challenging before the implementation of EPIC.

Similarly to EPIC, the Nuestros Niños Professional Development Programme was designed to support a specific subgroup: Latinx children with dual-language status in the United States. In previous years and today, significant academic achievement gaps persist between Latinx children and their native English-speaking counterparts (Pumar, 2021). There has also been evidence that these gaps are not only present at kindergarten entry but continue to widen over time (Buysse et al., 2010). Despite these concerning trends, research indicates that targeted, high-quality early education interventions can produce substantial gains for Latinx children in early literacy and other foundational skills (Buysse et al., 2010).

In response to these concerning trends regarding Latinx students, the Nuestros Niños Programme was developed. This programme complemented core classroom instruction by integrating educational strategies tailored to dual-language learners, alongside a professional development component to equip teachers with the necessary skills to effectively support Latinx students (Buysse et al., 2010).

The Nuestros Niños curriculum consisted of six modules, including "foundations for teaching language and literacy to dual language learners, bilingual oral language de-

velopment in young children, early literacy, early reading, early writing and an assessment of early language and literacy in young dual language learners” (Buysse et al. 2010, 198). These modules, coupled with the teacher training programs and bi-weekly results-driven evaluations, led to some positive results. Compared to students in control classrooms, the 92 students who were enrolled in the Nuestros Ninos Programme had greater gains on a standardized literacy activities rating scale, classroom observation scale and literacy environment checklist (Buysse et al., 2010). In observation classrooms, the frequency of literacy activities, quality of instructional practices and quality of literacy practices all increased significantly (Buysse et al., 2010).

Despite gains in classroom quality and targeted teaching, the achievement results for children were relatively modest, with evidence of positive effects only on a phonological awareness measure (Buysse et al., 2010). These achievement results, however, could be indicative of the study’s limited time frame and observational period, as the components of Nuestros Ninos curriculum are structured according to evidence-based practices that have proven effective for Latinx dual language students in previous instances.

Norway provides additional evidence of the effectiveness of targeted ECE programmes for migrant students. In 2006, to increase the participation of migrant children in ECE programmes, the Norwegian government implemented an intervention offering free childcare, four hours daily, in five districts in Oslo with the largest migrant populations (Drange & Telle, 2015). This intervention utilised pedagogical approaches tailored to the diverse needs of migrant children and offered language training to parents (Drange & Telle, 2015).

As a result of this initiative, the participation of migrant children in ECE programmes increased by 15% (Drange & Telle, 2015). In addition, enrolled children with immigrant backgrounds performed better at school entry tests than comparison children in differing districts (Drange & Telle, 2015). These children also performed better on

first grade tests and were about 5% more likely to score above average on both reading and mathematics assessments. In second grade, students produced similar high achievement results (Drange & Telle, 2015). Additionally, positive achievement results were higher among students with mothers unattached to the labour force. This means that the initiative not only lessened achievement gaps between migrant and majority population students but also students with low SES backgrounds and their more affluent peers.

While the previous ECE programmes focus on the benefits of targeted initiatives, other research points to potential drawbacks and negative consequences of this approach for children experiencing multiple disadvantages. In their study, Annika de Haan and colleagues evaluated the impacts of socioeconomically mixed preschools and kindergarten classrooms (de Haan et al., 2012). They specifically examined classrooms in which a targeted curriculum for socioeconomically disadvantaged children and teacher-led activities were implemented to gauge effects on the literacy and math skills of 3–6-year-old children facing disadvantages (de Haan et al., 2012).

The targeted curriculum used thematic learning techniques with aims to foster language, literacy and math skills, while focusing on core elements like increased small-group activities and one-on-one teacher instruction with students (de Haan et al., 2012). To facilitate high-level teacher engagement, teachers received eight half-days of specialised training and underwent numerous observations throughout the year (de Haan et al., 2012). Despite the targeted components of this initiative, de Haan and colleagues found that the number of teacher-led activities did not differ significantly between targeted and mixed classrooms (de Haan et al., 2012). Additionally, children in mixed classrooms, as opposed to targeted classrooms with all students from low socioeconomic backgrounds, gained more literacy and math skills (de Haan et al., 2012). While mixed classrooms produced some positive achievement effects, targeted classrooms produced no positive outcomes, most likely due to a lack of implementation fidelity amongst programme teachers regarding time spent on teacher-led activities (de Haan et al., 2012).

Overall findings revealed that students benefit from the diverse elements of mixed classrooms, as their more advantaged peers can facilitate increased co-learning and teachers are able to devote more attention to children with the most disadvantages (de Haan et al., 2012). More significantly, this research reveals the crucial role of qualified teachers. The researchers attribute the targeted program's lack of success to ineffective teacher practices.

Targeted ECE programmes also include those tailored to communal and local needs. There have been many localised ECE initiatives historically which have produced positive impacts for children facing disadvantages. One example is The Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative, designed to foster the early success of children in high-risk communities through teacher mentoring and high-quality community programmes (Bagnato et al., 2002). High-risk communities, in this context, refer to areas facing significant levels of poverty, where children are vulnerable to lower retention rates and higher special education placement rates compared to their peers (Bagnato et al., 2002). In collaboration with key stakeholders, including businesses, community leaders, parents and local experts, the Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative worked to ensure that all unserved children in these communities were enrolled in quality early childhood programmes (Bagnato et al., 2002).

The Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative combined an overarching structure with tailored programming to meet local needs. Despite variations in programmes due to local differences, they were evaluated using standardized tools and adhered to universal quality requirements (Bagnato et al., 2002). Universal features of the initiative included repeated consultations to ensure quality, intensive monitoring of standards, ongoing parental involvement, practices informed by child assessments and feedback and community-based leadership (Bagnato et al., 2002).

Many of the evaluation results of the Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative were positive. Rather than using a separate control group, the initiative assessed the children as their own controls, comparing each child's observed progress to their expected maturation (Bagnato et al., 2002). At the end of their kindergarten year, children who

participated in the initiative showed average to high average skills in spoken language, reading, writing and math (Bagnato et al., 2002). After participation in the programme, special education placement rates were also less than 1% (Bagnato et al., 2002). Over time, children who participated in the Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative consistently exceeded their expected developmental standards and demonstrated academic gains across multiple measures (Bagnato et al., 2002).

Similarly, the Sure Start Initiative in England, launched in 1999, aimed to enhance life chances for children and families in communities facing high levels of deprivation (Eisenstadt, 2011). Sure Start Local Programmes were community-led and designed with a high degree of autonomy to ensure that local needs were met (Melhuish et al., 2008). Like the Pittsburgh Initiative, Sure Start programmes were anchored in core standards, such as outreach and home visiting services, support for quality play and learning and primary healthcare, promoting access to these essential services through a “one stop shop” in the community, a local access point for services that a parent could visit with the child (Melhuish et al., 2008).

Initial evaluations of Sure Start revealed mixed outcomes. In an early evaluation in 2006, researchers discovered that Sure Start Local Programmes produced beneficial effects such as better parenting and better social functioning in children for non-teenaged mothers (Belsky et al., 2006). For teenaged mothers and single parent households, however, proximity to SSLPS showed adverse effects like poorer social functioning and lower verbal ability (Belsky et al., 2006). Due to the evidence of adverse effects for the most disadvantaged children, Sure Start stakeholders further developed the programme.

During the second wave of evaluations, three-year-olds with access to a Sure Start Centre showed increased social and behavioural developments with no evidence of adverse effects (Melhuish et al., 2008). When retroactively examining the impact of having access to a Sure Start Centre on children ages 0 through 4, Carneiro et al. (2025) found that children within a 2.5 kilometre distance of a Sure Start Centre

showed improved dimensions of school readiness regarding communication, language and problem solving, which are closely related to later English and mathematics competencies.

Following its initial evaluations, Sure Start evolved by transitioning from local programmes to Children's Centres, aiming to expand its reach to the most disadvantaged families (Sammons et al., 2015). Through three waves of evaluations, Sure Start Children's Centres demonstrated some evidence of positive outcomes in improving child behavioural and social skills, with more modest gains in cognitive development (Sammons et al., 2015).

The Peers Early Education Partnership and Australia's Communities for Children Initiative also prioritized community and family engagement, which led to impacts in participant development (Evangelou et al., 2007; Katz et al., 2010). Both initiatives tailored their programmes to meet local needs and ensured continuous parental involvement. Children in these programmes showed substantial improvements in vocabulary, phonological awareness, early numeracy skills and other early learning milestones (Evangelou et al., 2007; Katz et al., 2010). The positive student outcomes were also accompanied by concurrent improvements in parental and household engagement, further reinforcing the many successes of these programmes.

Although some evaluations of the previous community and family-based initiatives found evidence of neutral or slightly negative effects, each of these also revealed some positive outcomes. The United States Comprehensive Child Development Programme, a family-based initiative with similar intentions as the above programmes, did not lead to any statistically significant impacts or benefits on participants when compared to control families (Goodson et al., 2000).

The Comprehensive Child Development Programme was established to serve infants and young children in families with incomes below the federal poverty line who faced multiple disadvantages (Goodson et al., 2000). This programme, like other family-

based initiatives, obtained a core set of guidelines and services. However, these services were delivered mainly through home visits, where case workers assisted parents and their children on varying activities and conducted familial assessments to determine needs (Goodson et al., 2000).

Despite a lack of certainty, the absence of statistically significant impacts from this programme, could indicate that family-based programmes alone, especially through home visits, are insufficient to adequately address the needs of children facing multiple disadvantages. The results of this study can be corroborated with the aforementioned initiatives to reveal that parental and community involvement, coupled with spaces like children's centres, lead to more positive achievement results for children.

Universal ECE programmes/ expansions

While targeted early childhood education practices and initiatives have often proven effective in promoting academic achievement amongst children facing disadvantages, evidence also suggests that simply increasing access to early education can lead to positive outcomes for disadvantaged groups (Barnett, 2008).

Addressing the Western-centric biases often present in early childhood education research, this review includes examples from non-Western contexts. One prominent early childhood initiative in China is its One Village One Preschool Project, a government-backed initiative providing fully funded early education to disadvantaged and minority children in rural areas (Chen et al., 2019). By establishing 2,300 centres across ten provinces, the project has had positive impacts on children's academic outcomes (Chen et al., 2019).

Children enrolled in the One Village One Preschool Project demonstrated significantly higher rates of academic improvement and attained superior elementary school scores compared to those who did not participate in early education or were

enrolled in underfunded programmes (Chen et al., 2019). While programme participants showed lower achievement scores compared to children in more affluent areas, the growth rates were similar, suggesting that the initiative is effective at closing educational gaps, especially when supported by sufficient resources.

Bangladesh provides another successful example of an early childhood intervention aimed at children from rural and disadvantaged communities (Aboud, 2006). In this initiative, preschools offered half-day programmes six days a week to children from underprivileged areas, focusing on core elements like child-led play, storytelling, literacy and math instruction (Aboud, 2006). The results were compelling, suggesting that children who participated in the preschool programmes outperformed their peers, children with similar demographic backgrounds who did not attend preschool. Results manifested in improved outcomes as measured by vocabulary, verbal reasoning, nonverbal reasoning and overall school readiness (Aboud, 2006).

Germany has also experienced an expansion of early childhood education initiatives since the early 2000s (Ghirardi et al., 2023). Historically, Germany has offered some form of early childhood education and care for working families, mostly targeted at children over three. Since 2013, however, Germany has expanded legal entitlement to ECE to children one year and older (Ghirardi et al., 2023). Despite this expansion, participation rates of children under three have remained relatively low.

To determine the effects of Germany's expansion of ECE programmes, Gaia Ghirardi et al. (2023) utilised the new-born sample of the National Education Panel Study, examining the social and cognitive competencies of children under three after attending these programmes. Ghirardi et al. not only found that the probability of attending ECE programmes differed by socio-economic status, but the impact of such programmes also varied according to this factor (Ghirardi et al., 2023). More specifically, children from wealthier backgrounds were about 1.3 times more likely to attend ECE programmes than children from lower socio-economic backgrounds (Ghirardi et al., 2023). Regarding impact, however, attending ECE programmes improved

the mathematics and vocabulary skills of children from low-socioeconomic backgrounds, while being ineffective and even detrimental for children from higher socioeconomic backgrounds (Ghirardi et al., 2023). These findings are in line with previous research, suggesting that ECE programmes can function as equalising mechanisms, diminishing the educational gaps between children.

When evaluating the impact of preschool on language development among Turkish immigrants in Germany, Oliver Klein and Birgit Becker found similar positive results. Preschool education in Germany is voluntary, yet highly subsidised, granting every child legal entitlement to attend an ECE programme (Klein & Becker, 2017). German preschools also operate with explicit aims of promoting language development. As such, Klein and Becker found that for children from Turkish backgrounds, preschool attendance for 36 months, 26 hours per week improves German vocabulary by 25 percentage points (Klein & Becker, 2017).

These positive findings were only associated with children of Turkish origin with less advanced German language skills, as opposed to students from the majority population and other students with Turkish origins whose parents spoke German at home (Klein & Becker, 2017). When considering preschool quality, Klein and Becker observed that preschools which offer more access to books increase the test scores of Turkish-migrant students by 31.5 percentage points compared to 24.2 percentage points when children attend lower quality schools (Klein & Becker, 2017). These students also achieved higher vocabulary results in preschools with lower child-staff ratios (Klein & Becker, 2017). These results suggest that preschool attendance is a particularly important first step for migrants with less advanced vocabulary skills than their peers. However, preschool quality matters, as higher quality preschools further mitigate the educational gaps for disadvantaged students.

Like Germany, the Netherlands has undergone an expansion of ECE, allowing children to enrol in primary school as early as the day after their fourth birthday (Leuven et al., 2010). By allowing children to enrol immediately after their fourth birthday, as opposed to the beginning of the school year, children have the potential to receive 11

additional weeks of educational support (Leuven et al., 2010). When evaluating this programme, researchers found that even one additional month of schooling increases the language and math scores of disadvantaged students, while having no effect on non-disadvantaged students (Leuven et al., 2010). For students from minority backgrounds, the educational impact of an extra month of schooling is even higher, raising their language scores by 7 percent of a standard deviation as opposed to 5 percent for disadvantaged Dutch students (Leuven et al., 2010). Overall, one additional month of schooling closes the achievement gap between disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged students by around 10 percent (Leuven et al., 2010).

Long Term Evaluations

Despite the positive early achievement gains noted in many preschool evaluation outcomes, there is growing concern among researchers, policymakers and stakeholders regarding the lasting impact of these benefits. For disadvantaged children, early academic improvements, while notable, often fade over time due to factors like quality of subsequent educational institutions in terms of resources and staff ratio, ongoing vulnerability and the overall socio-economic context (Zhai et al., 2012). To better understand the enduring effects of early childhood education and evaluate its impact on long-term academic success, longitudinal studies are essential. Therefore, this systematic review incorporates these studies to ensure a comprehensive analysis of sustained academic benefits resulting from early childhood interventions.

Launched in 1984, the South Carolina Early Childhood Development Programme for Four-Year-Olds aimed to support children from low-income families by providing half and full-day services designed to enhance school readiness. The first evaluation of the programme revealed significant improvements on early assessments, including above average scores on school readiness tests (Yao & Hearn, 2003).

In a subsequent longitudinal study, researchers compared performances on standardised tests of those who participated in the programme and their similarly situated peers (Yao & Hearn, 2003). Upon attending the South Carolina Early Childhood Programme as four-year-olds, students scored significantly higher than their peers on first and third grade standardized tests for English and mathematics (Yao & Hearn, 2003). In second grade, students also scored higher than their peers, however, these differences lacked statistical significance (Yao & Hearn, 2003). Regarding subgroup effects, it was determined that girls, and Caucasian and Asian students, benefitted more from the programme, as these students were most likely to achieve the best results on achievement measures (Yao & Hearn, 2003). Given the extreme levels of disadvantage amongst the participants within this programme and the high risk of academic failure these children faced prior to programme implementation, the evidence of longer-term benefits is of particular importance.

The Head Start Programme, launched in 1965, was one of the most prolific early childhood programmes in the United States, igniting a surge of initiatives inspired by its model across the globe. Unlike previous early childhood programmes in the US., Head Start had substantial federal funding to support the programme's efforts to address school readiness gaps between disadvantaged children and their peers (Kim, 2013). As such, Head Start Programmes experienced staggering enrolment rates, with over 900,000 children participating across all US states (Kim, 2013).

Given the magnitude of Head Start and substantial funding by the federal government, teams of evaluators reviewed Head Start Programmes in various stages. In an early study McKey et al. (1985), found that Head Start led to positive outcomes on cognitive and physical measures, with some effects fading upon entrance to elementary school. Other researchers found that, when compared to siblings who did not attend Head Start or attended a different programme, Head Start attendees were more likely to achieve higher test scores and less likely to repeat grades (Currie & Thomas, 1995). These results, however, were the most significant amongst white students (Currie & Thomas, 1995).

Nianbo Dong found that when compared to other centre-based care programmes in ordinary least square models, Head Start participants performed worse in reading and math in kindergarten, with no statistically significant effects for retention (Dong, 2009). However, when using sensitivity intervals to evaluate impact, Dong found no statistically significant difference between Head Start participants and those in other centre-based programs on reading and math achievement (Dong, 2009).

Regarding longer-term evaluations, Aughinbaugh (2001) found no effects on grade repetition, school suspension or math test scores when Head Start students were teenagers. Alternatively, other studies found positive effects on academic achievement for white and black Head Start students during this period (Ludwig & Miller, 2007; Deming, 2009).

The inconsistencies within studies regarding the short- and long-term effects of Head Start provide researchers with more questions for investigation. In their study Young-Joo Kim examined the effects of Head Start during the first four years of school after completion of the programme (Kim, 2013). Through this investigation, Kim discovered evidence of ample measurement error in parental reports of Head Start attendance, as some students who were reportedly in Head Start were not enrolled but attended other programmes (Kim, 2013). After accounting for these errors, Kim found that African American Head Start attendees made significant improvements in test scores, especially in math, when compared to students from similar demographic backgrounds (Kim, 2013). For other groups, particularly white and Latinx students, there were much smaller effects on reading and math test scores (Kim, 2013).

When considering the diverse and varying findings from Head Start evaluations, Kim's study points to one reason behind the inconclusive results. It is notable, however, that even despite accounting for measurement bias in favour of Head Start Programmes, there is still evidence of academic improvement amongst participants.

Therese Pigott et al. (2005) also wrote about discrepancies in evaluations of Head Start programmes, emphasizing the necessity of a clear use of social categories to

denote learners, when determining programme effectiveness for disadvantaged children. In this study, researchers examined the reading and math assessment scores of Head Start participants, comparing the results to same-aged children after entrance to kindergarten (Pigott et al., 2005). It was discovered that when compared to children of a similar socio-economic status, Head Start participants scored higher than their peers (Pigott et al., 2005). Alternatively, when compared to more affluent children, achievement gaps remained prevalent (Pigott et al., 2005). This article suggests that Head Start provided a positive initial foundation for children facing multiple disadvantages, but more must be done to ensure that no child gets left behind due to socio-economic status.

This section has examined and analysed the effectiveness of a broad range of ECE programmes, according to measures of academic achievement for children facing disadvantages. It shows that carefully designed targeted interventions, such as EPIC, Nuestros Niños and Norway's free preschool initiative, can produce meaningful gains in specific skill areas, though results often depend on implementation quality and adequate teacher training.

Community-based models like the Pittsburgh Early Childhood Initiative and England's Sure Start further demonstrate that interventions which respond to local needs for education, family support and community engagement, and provide in this sense holistic services, can improve children's readiness and development. Notably, holistic services are beneficial in a longer-term perspective, while initial outcomes are mixed.

Universal expansions of ECE emerged in our review, as seen in countries such as China, Bangladesh, Germany and the Netherlands. The results from these studies indicate that simply increasing access to early learning opportunities can narrow achievement gaps, with especially strong benefits for children from low-income or migrant backgrounds. This applies notably when programme quality is moderate to high. Long-term evaluations, including those of major U.S. programmes like Head Start and the South Carolina Early Childhood Development Programme, reveal more varied results: early gains sometimes fade, but certain groups, particularly the most

disadvantaged, continue to experience some lasting academic advantages. Collectively, the evidence underscores that ECE can be a powerful equalizer in terms of academic achievement and advancement, but its success depends on program design, quality, teacher expertise and sustained support.

Behaviour

This section will explore the effectiveness of early childhood interventions on children facing multiple disadvantages, with a focus on behavioural measures like socio-emotional and problem-solving skills. There is an abundance of evidence suggesting that children's socio-emotional competencies are significant predictors of future academic and life outcomes (Rosenthal & Gatt, 2010). For disadvantaged children in particular, the cultivation of socio-emotional skills has the potential for further benefit, as these groups are often exposed to increased stressors (Rosenthal & Gatt, 2010).

Table three presents an overview of the articles in this section.

Image: Adobe Stock, stock.adobe.com

Table 3: Behavioural Advancement Outcomes of Early Childhood Education Interventions

Subtheme	Author(s) (Year)	Country/ Context	Intervention Type	Study Design	Key Behavioural Findings
Targeted Programs	Bierman et al. (2013)	USA	REDI curriculum (Head Start)	RCT	Reduced aggressive behaviour; improved social problem-solving
	Bierman et al. (2016)	USA	REDI + home-visiting	Longitudinal	Sustained socio-emotional and classroom engagement benefits
Community-Based Programs	Melhuish et al. (2010)	England	Sure Start	Quasi-experimental	Neutral short-term behavioural effects
	Carneiro et al. (2025)	England	Sure Start	Longitudinal	Reduced internalising behaviours; lower mental health hospitalisations
Universal / Centre-Based ECE	Votruba-Drzal et al. (2015)	USA	Centre-based ECE	Longitudinal	Improved behavioural functioning for migrant children
	Alvarado-Suárez & Acosta-González (2022)	Ecuador	CDI Program	Quasi-experimental	Increased socio-emotional skills with longer exposure
	Melhuish et al. (2017)	England	SEED Programme	Longitudinal	Mixed effects; early behavioural challenges followed by later gains
Long-Term Evaluations	Zhai et al. (2012)	USA	Chicago School Readiness Project	Longitudinal	Behavioural benefits only sustained in high-quality schools
	Xie et al. (2020)	USA	Perry Pre-school	Longitudinal	Reduced externalising behaviour; strong non-cognitive skill formation

Targeted Programs

This section begins by examining the effects of another integrated Head Start Curriculum. As evidenced by previous sections of this review, the magnitude and popularity of Head Start was conducive to the implementation of novel curricula within its programmes. In their studies, Karen Bierman et al. (2013 & 2016) examine student outcomes according to their participation in the Research-Based, Developmentally Informed (REDI) intervention within Head Start.

REDI was created to provide more comprehensive and effective programmes for children facing multiple disadvantages through an evidence-based curriculum and teacher training tools (Bierman et al., 2013). In addition, REDI included aspects of the Preschool PATHS (Promoting Alternative Thinking Strategies) Curriculum. Put together, REDI's integrated curriculum focused on core components such as reading and phonological awareness training and the promotion of socio-emotional skills (Bierman et al., 2013). After one year of participation in the REDI intervention, Bierman's study revealed that REDI promoted kindergarten phonemic decoding skills, learning engagement and competent social problem-solving skills, while reducing aggressive-disruptive behaviours (Bierman et al. 2013, 140).

After determining the effects of REDI on children's outcomes one year later Bierman et al. conducted another study which examined outcomes three years after exposure. This study evaluated the effects of a typical Head Start Programme, a Head Start Programme with the REDI curriculum and a Head Start Programme with the REDI curriculum and a home-visiting intervention when children were in third grade. The REDI curriculum included the same core components, with specific modules focusing on interactive reading programmes, sound games, activities to promote phonological awareness and strategies to facilitate socio-emotional development (Bierman et al., 2016). The home-visiting intervention provided another targeted tool to increase parental support and involvement in home learning (Bierman et al., 2016).

When evaluated according to levels of effectiveness, researchers found that relative to typical head start programmes, the REDI intervention alone led to benefits in socio-emotional skills, improving classroom behaviours like participation, peer and student-teacher relationships and social competencies (Bierman et al., 2016). The REDI intervention, coupled with the home-visiting component, led to mental health benefits for children through improved social competencies and peer relationships as well as better academic performance (Bierman et al., 2016).

Taken together, these programmes exemplify the potential benefits of evidence-based curricula and targeted programmes for disadvantaged groups. Each of these initiatives, the REDI curriculum and the home-visiting programme, produced benefits for children facing multiple disadvantages, but together these initiatives led to enhanced achievement and behavioural impacts.

When evaluating Sure Start according to its impact on behavioural functioning and skill development, researchers found mixed results. In an initial study, five-year-olds with access to Sure Start showed no difference in self-regulation skills compared to peers who did not live near a Sure Start Centre (Melhuish et al., 2010). There were also no differences in emotional dysregulation, positive social behaviour or internalising behaviours (National Evaluation of Sure Start (NESS) Team, 2012).

On the other hand, Pedro Carneiro et al. (2025) found that children with access to Sure Start from an early age experienced lower levels of internalising behaviours, resulting in less depressive and anxiety disorders at older ages (Carneiro et al., 2025). Children with greater access to Sure Start programmes than their siblings also revealed half as many internalising difficulties (Carneiro et al., 2025). Additionally, access to Sure Start reduced mental-health related hospitalisations at ages 12-14 by around 50% of the baseline (Carneiro et al., 2025). Compared to short-term findings, these results emphasise that initial exposure to an ECE programme may not lead to immediate benefits. In the long term, however, the benefits of early programmes often become more cemented and can be seen in students exposed to these interventions.

Universal ECE programmes/ expansions

Several studies throughout this systematic review, and within the literature more generally, examine and evaluate centre-based ECE programmes. These programmes, providing early years learning and behavioural development at early childhood education centres, have been linked to some academic and behavioural improvements for disadvantaged populations (Votruba-Drzal et al., 2015).

In the United States researchers studied the initial effects of generalised, centre-based programmes on immigrant children upon entrance to kindergarten (Votruba-Drzal et al., 2015). They found that programmes embedded in early childhood education centres are associated with increased math, reading, and language skills as well as enhanced behavioural functioning for many migrant groups (Votruba-Drzal et al., 2015). Significantly, these positive outcomes remained despite migrant country of origin and background (Votruba-Drzal et al., 2015).

In another context, Ecuador, the Centros de Desarrollo Infantil (CDI) Programme provides free centre-based early childhood education to vulnerable children (Alvarado-Suarez & Acosta-Gonzalez, 2022). This programme specifically assists pregnant mothers and children up to age three through education services five days a week and food services four times a day in 2085 centres nationwide (Alvarado-Suarez & Acosta-Gonzalez, 2022). In an evaluation of its effectiveness, researchers found that as a child's exposure to a CDI Programme increased, so did their cognitive and socio-emotional skills (Alvarado-Suarez & Acosta-Gonzalez, 2022).

Some behavioural outcomes of centre-based early childhood education programmes provide more mixed results. In the Early Education and Development study, researchers evaluated the effectiveness of England's expansion of fully funded early education for two-year-olds from the most disadvantaged households (Melhuish et al., 2017). Initial findings revealed that more hours in formal ECE programmes were linked to outcomes such as weaker prosocial behaviours and emotional regulation (Melhuish et al., 2017). It was also found that more hours in formal childcare led to an increased risk of socio-emotional problems in year one (Melhuish et al., 2017).

Further review and additional census data analysis revealed that formal ECE was associated with some factors of socio-emotional development, like increased prosocial behaviour and fewer peer problems (Melhuish et al., 2017). These subsequent findings suggest that positive behavioural impacts of ECE could take time, as young children who enter centre-based programmes often undergo an adjustment period before being able to reap positive cognitive and behavioural benefits.

Long-Term Evaluations

Many initial evaluations of early childhood education programmes reveal positive benefits for children. As children progress through their educational journeys, however, there is evidence of progress fading out (Zhai et al., 2012). Researchers evaluating data from the Chicago School Readiness Project, a well-known centre-based project for children from lower socio-economic backgrounds, examine the effects of the programme on kindergarten outcomes based on school quality (Zhai et al., 2012). Fuhua Zhai et al. (2012) find that participation in the intervention led to significant behavioural and achievement outcomes when students subsequently attended a high-performing school. However, when students attended a low-performing school, there were no significant effects (Zhai et al., 2012).

The High Scope Perry Preschool Programme was implemented in the United States in 1962 and has undergone a series of in-depth evaluations to determine its effects. The success of the High Scope Perry Preschool Programme is often attributed to its substantial enhancement of non-cognitive skills, which have led to “reduced externalising behaviour, improved academic motivation, and increased openness to experience [...and] higher educational attainment, higher income, and lower criminal misconduct than those of the controlled subjects” (Xie et al., 2020, 4). When examining subgroup effects, researchers determined that enrolment in the High Scope Perry Preschool Programme on cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes were even greater for the most disadvantaged children (Xie et al., 2020). They also found evidence of

positive cyclical effects regarding the most disadvantaged groups, as preschool enrolment tended to impact early cognitive gains, leading to the formation of greater non-cognitive skills, which further enhanced later cognitive gains (Xie et al., 2020).

This section has focused on the assessment of ECE programmes on the mitigation of educational inequalities for children facing disadvantages according to behavioural outcomes. Through an analysis of 9 studies, this section reveals that evidence-based, targeted curricula, especially combined with localised components, can produce numerous behavioural benefits for disadvantaged children. There is also evidence that more generalised centre-based ECE programmes can lead to increased socio-emotional skills and behavioural functioning for migrant children and other disadvantaged groups.

On the other hand, some ECE evaluation results suggest mixed and negative outcomes for disadvantaged children, including weaker prosocial behaviours and emotional regulation skills. In some cases, these weak outcomes could be due to early evaluation procedures, as behavioural outcomes can become more cemented with time and age. This section also examines the significance of subsequent levels of quality education in terms of progress fade-out and sedimentation, particularly given that early behavioural skills are often developed in ECE Programmes but fade with later schooling.

Retention

As alluded to throughout the previous sections, long-term systemic outcomes of ECE in the form of sustained effects of achievement and behavioural development are not measurable by empirical studies that assess individual programmes or interventions that have focused on documenting immediately measurable changes. This highlights an important point for the field of early childhood education. The lasting impacts of early childhood interventions are not only significant for programme participants but also for stakeholders and policymakers who intend to fund these initiatives with long-term outcomes in mind and who need to contextualise interventions in policy frameworks that can support sustained outcomes. Through evaluations measuring retention, stakeholders are more accurately equipped to determine what works for children facing multiple disadvantages in the short, medium, and long term, enabling them to create interventions which mitigate intergenerational cycles of poverty and enhance outcomes for society at large.

Table four outlines the articles in this section.

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Table 4: Retention and Long-Term Outcomes of Early Childhood Education Interventions

Subtheme	Author(s) (Year)	Country/Context	Intervention Type	Study Design	Key Retention Findings
Educational Retention	Phillips et al. (2016)	USA	Tulsa CAP Head Start	Longitudinal	Higher grade retention; reduced chronic absenteeism
	Reynolds et al. (2001)	USA	Chicago Child-Parent Centre	Longitudinal	Higher high-school completion; fewer grade drop-outs
Higher Education & Employment	Campbell et al. (2002)	USA	Abecedarian Project	Longitudinal	Increased college attendance and degree completion
	Havnes & Mogstad (2011)	Norway	Subsidised childcare reform	Longitudinal	Reduced drop-out; increased college participation
Crime & Social Outcomes	Campbell et al. (2008)	USA	Project CARE	Longitudinal	Reduced drug use; improved vocational outcomes
	Carneiro et al. (2024)	England	Sure Start	Longitudinal	Lower youth crime and custodial sentences
	Reynolds et al. (2001)	USA	Child-Parent Centre	Longitudinal	Reduced juvenile arrests and violent crime

Long-Term Evaluations

The scale of evaluations which focus on retention outcomes are long-term. This research is pivotal to include when determining the sustained effects of programme

participation over time on measures like dropout rates, matriculation into higher education, incarceration and crime rates and other life outcomes.

To investigate the effects of a preschool programme on middle school students, Deborah Phillips et al. (2016) evaluated student outcomes in eighth grade based on student participation in the Tulsa, Oklahoma Community Action Project, a local Head Start Programme. Compared to their peers who had not participated in the Tulsa Community Action Project but subsequently attended Tulsa Public Schools, programme participants achieved higher test scores in math and had higher rates of grade retention, with less chronic absenteeism (Phillips et al., 2016). Subgroup effects remained positive, with increased grade retention for girls and students eligible for free lunch, less chronic absenteeism for girls, Hispanic students and students eligible for free lunch, and higher math test scores for white students, Hispanic students and students eligible for free lunch (Phillips et al., 2016).

The United States' Abecedarian Project and Project Care were erected at similar time periods with comparable goals to target and improve the life chances of children from low-income backgrounds at risk of developmental delays and school failure (Campbell et al., 2008).

Project Care included intervention groups who received centre-based education, education through home-visitation alone and a control group. This project emphasised the necessity of programmes based at ECE-centres for increased cognitive and social skills, as no positive effects were found in the family education component alone (Campbell et al., 2008). Regarding the long-term effects of Project Care, researchers found evidence of educational and vocational gains, along with decreased levels of marijuana usage and more active lifestyles amongst participants (Campbell et al., 2008).

In evaluations of the Abecedarian Project, researchers found that children who had received the centre-based preschool intervention achieved better test results and higher academic performance measures when compared to their peers (Campbell et

al., 2002). As adults, participants in the Abecedarian Project showed increased educational and vocational achievement gains, with effect sizes for reading and math remaining persistent (Campbell et al., 2002). Participants were also more likely to attend a four-year college, have decreased marijuana usage, more active lifestyles, less rates of teen pregnancy and fewer children than those of the same age with similar demographic backgrounds (Campbell et al., 2002).

In Norway, impacts of an ECE reform, leading to a large-scale expansion of subsidised childcare in 1975, were evaluated according to adult outcomes (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011). Researchers found that this expansion of subsidised childcare had substantial outcomes on participants, as measured at age 30 (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011). Children in these programmes completed more levels of education, with programmes decreasing the probability of high school dropouts by nearly 6 percentage points and increasing college participation by almost 7 percentage points (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011). The most substantial educational impacts of this reform were on children with low-educated mothers (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011).

Children enrolled in subsidised ECE also revealed evidence of increased labour market participation (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011). These programmes significantly decreased the chances of children having little to no adult earnings, while also mitigating welfare dependency and promoting delayed childbearing (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011). The most substantial market impacts of this reform were on girls (Havnes & Mogstad, 2011).

Numerous articles have also investigated the impact of ECE programmes on adult incarceration and crime rates. These outcomes are significant to this study and early childhood education programmes in general because they can indicate children's welfare through interactions with social services, the youth justice system and other social care programmes (Carneiro et al., 2024).

An additional long-term evaluation of the Abecedarian Project revealed mixed findings regarding incarceration and crime outcomes. When attendees were evaluated at

age 30, involvement in criminal activities did not vary significantly dependent on programme participation (Campbell et al., 2012). Despite the neutral findings regarding incarceration rates, researchers discovered that by age 30 those who participated in the Abecedarian Project obtained significantly large educational gains, with more degree years completed and higher college graduation rates than their similar counterparts (Campbell et al., 2012). Programme participants also had higher levels of long-term and full-time employment. However, there was no evidence of statistically significant results on income levels (Campbell et al., 2012).

In their studies evaluating the Chicago Child-Parent Centre Programme and the Sure Start Programme, respectively, Reynolds et al. (2001) and Carneiro et al. (2024) examine the effects of these initiatives on youth misbehaviour and crime.

The Chicago Child-Parent Centre Programme, like Sure Start, was erected to provide early childhood education, family and health services to children from impoverished backgrounds (Reynolds et al., 2001). With a staggering 80% participation rate, this programme served thousands of children in the most disadvantaged areas throughout Chicago (Reynolds et al., 2001). Researchers found that those who participated in the Chicago Child-Parent Centre Programme had a significantly higher rate of high school completion at age 20, a lower school-dropout rate and completed more years of education than those who did not participate (Reynolds et al., 2001). For boys, school dropout rates amongst programme participants were even lower, which is remarkably significant given that, at the time, Black men were at the highest risk of school failure, and this program predominately served African American children and their families (Reynolds et al., 2001).

When examining juvenile arrest rates, it was discovered that arrest rates of previous programme participants were significantly lower than their peers (Reynolds et al., 2001). Additionally, preschool programme participants had lower rates of multiple and violent arrests, with extended participation in a program leading to even fewer violent arrests (Reynolds et al., 2001).

This study points to the crucial role preschool participation can afford to children facing multiple disadvantages, as lower arrest rates were not associated with school-age programme participation (Reynolds et al., 2001). Despite these positive results, it is significant to consider that school drop-out and arrest rates for programme participants still exceed the average for children nationally (Reynolds et al., 2001).

Retention and incarceration outcomes for Sure Start participants are more mixed. In their report, Carneiro et al. (2024) found that secondary school suspension rates for children who had access to Sure Start Centres increased by 10%, while rates of absenteeism simultaneously increased by 7% (Carneiro et al., 2024).

Regarding positive long-term outcomes, the researchers discovered that children between the ages of three and four, with access to a nearby Sure Start Centre, had lower youth crime rates resulting in convictions or custodial sentences. Additionally, living within 2.5 kilometres of a Sure Start Centre reduced the rate of 16-year-olds with criminal convictions by 13% (Carneiro et al., 2024). As a result of access to Sure Start, custodial sentences also fell by a fifth, with 20% reductions on both theft convictions and drug offenses (Carneiro et al., 2024).

Mixed results also came from evaluations regarding contact with the criminal justice system and evidence of misbehaviour more generally (Carneiro et al., 2024). Children with access to Sure Start programmes were found to commit offenses at earlier ages than their peers, receiving higher rates of caution for criminal damage and violent crime (Carneiro et al., 2024). By age 12, these children showed a 10% increase in rates of less serious misdemeanours. However, overall numbers of young people who received cautions by age 16 were unchanged (Carneiro et al., 2024).

This section reveals some long-term impacts of ECE programmes on disadvantaged children, including lower dropout rates, completion of additional levels of education, delayed childbearing, increases in labour market participation, and decreases in welfare dependency, drug usage and criminal convictions. Although there are mixed

findings throughout some of the reports, this section indicates that ECE has substantial potential to contribute to the long-term outcomes, including contributing to the mitigation of intergenerational cycles of poverty amongst disadvantaged groups.

Discussion and Conclusion

This systematic review provides an overview of the growing landscape of early childhood education initiatives since the year 2000. Attention was directed at interventions targeting children with migrant, minority or low SES status and children who represent a combination of these social categories. In this study, we have examined ECE interventions and evaluations in various contexts through researchers' differing methodological approaches. Our emphasis is on strategies and tools which have repeatedly contributed to reductions in inequalities in educational outcomes and which reveal contextually dependent examples of successful ECE interventions.

One of the most salient findings in this review, consistent with other systematic reviews in the field, is that the mere implementation of early childhood programmes in disadvantaged communities can contribute meaningfully to the mitigation of educational inequalities amongst disadvantaged students, especially when supported by adequate resources and trained teachers. While many benefits of ECE programmes vary contextually and can decrease with time, there is evidence that ECE offers children in under-resourced settings a more equitable start to life across diverse global settings.

Another key finding is the increased prevalence and significance of targeted ECE interventions. As stakeholders seek to enhance the effectiveness of ECE programmes, particularly for children facing barriers to education, there is a growing emphasis on approaches grounded in research and data. Research based models that target needs of specific social groups are especially responsive to the unique developmental needs of children from lower socio-economic backgrounds or with migrant experiences (Buysse et al., 2010). The targeted approach has, in many cases, demonstrated comparatively greater effectiveness in supporting diverse learning trajectories (Fantuzzo et al., 2011).

Importantly, not all evidence-based interventions are academic in nature. Many are community or family-centred, designed in response to local needs. Landmark programmes such as Head Start and Sure Start exemplify this approach, having served as foundational models for subsequent interventions.

Almost all of the familial and community-centred models in this review provide evidence of effectiveness for children facing multiple disadvantages. Family and community-centred models are conducive for supporting stakeholders and policymakers to more adequately assess and determine relative needs. The most effective of these programmes have local and centralized components which provide universal frameworks implemented across localities. These programmes have also been found to be more successful when they include activities at a local centre, as opposed to only home-visiting components (Goodson et al. 2000). There is evidence of the significance of familial and community involvement in the development and dissemination of early childhood programmes, but there must also be top-down mechanisms to ensure educational benefits.

The examination of retention measures and long-term evaluations provides positive results, despite some mixed outcomes. These findings emphasise, in part, the difficulty of evaluating initial or short-term interventions, as outcomes over time are likely to be more salient and diffuse. It is for this reason that results regarding the reduction of educational inequalities and promotion of equity and inclusion in ECE interventions are better discerned several years later and best appear in system level comparisons. As such, sustained investment in ECE through universal policies and efforts to expand access to publicly funded ECE are highly recommended to governments interested in implementing these policies.

In this study, all the evaluated interventions have resulted in some positive long-term effects in domains like higher education, crime reduction, positive family outcomes and welfare dependency. Given increasing concerns about the dissipation of benefits overtime, these studies suggest that quality early childhood programmes implemented in disadvantaged communities can lead to remarkable differences in adult

outcomes and work to mitigate welfare dependency and intergenerational cycles of poverty. For stakeholders and policymakers intending to fund early childhood programmes, these are some of the most influential results emphasising the significance of these initiatives.

This evidence also reveals that if sustained access to inclusive ECE interventions is not adopted, governments will pay a penalty in the form of higher health care expenses due to the increased likelihood of public healthcare problems to do with absenteeism, alienation and mental health issues in youth populations. Additionally, in line with Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1962) and studies on typologies of Welfare regimes (Esping-Andersen, 1990), this study emphasises that a lacking investment in universal sustained policies for equitable access to ECE, is associated with a greater need for welfare programmes and a loss of workforce that thereby has a negative impact on the development of the national economy. Lacking universal policies to support public ECE is associated with a weaker ability of the population to participate in society, education and the labour force. Outcomes will not show in full immediately. However, if ECE policies are implemented effectively and sustained, the likelihood of reduced societal costs can be remarkably high.

While there remains scope for improvement in the design and implementation of early childhood interventions, this systematic review provides a robust synthesis of the available evidence on effective practices. The strength of the conclusions drawn from this review is largely attributable to the inclusion of longitudinal and quasi-experimental studies, which allow for more credible inferences regarding programme impacts over time. These findings underscore the importance of sustained collaboration between policymakers, academic institutions, evaluators, practitioners and community stakeholders in both the development and assessment of early childhood initiatives.

Nevertheless, several limitations should be acknowledged. The search strategy relied exclusively on Google Scholar and was restricted to the first 1,000 results. This approach may have omitted relevant studies from discipline-specific databases and

introduced selection bias, as Google Scholar's ranking algorithm prioritises citation metrics over methodological quality. Consequently, the findings represent a significant, but not exhaustive, overview of the literature. Future studies should employ a multi-database search strategy (e.g., Scopus, PsycINFO, or ERIC) and utilise unbiased screening protocols that prioritise methodological rigour over citation rankings.

To conclude, the findings in this report emphasise the significance of investment in ECE programmes, policies and initiatives. ECE not only has the potential to level the playing field for children facing compound disadvantages but also can lead to remarkable long-term outcomes for these groups. Therefore, additional research should be done to further understand the most impactful ECE methods and initiatives for children. More significantly, policymakers should use studies like this which focus on longitudinal research to more effectively understand and target educational inequalities across groups, informing equitable and context-sensitive early childhood policies which lead to positive impacts in the short, medium and long term.

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Project Name: Strategies for Achieving Equity and Inclusion in Education, Training and Learning in Democratic Europe (STRIDE)

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- Roehampton University (RU), United Kingdom
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